

**ETHIOPIAN SPACE SCIENCE
SOCIETY DAMBI DOLLO
BRANCH**

Dambi Dollo University's Researcher attended ESSGA 20 on behalf of ESSS Dambi Dollo Branch Association

Compiled by:

Abduselam Mohammed Yasin (ESSS Dambi Dollo Branch Chairperson)

May 25, 2025

No	Name	Education Level	Role in ESSSDBA	Remark
1	Abduselam Mohammed	MSc	Chairperson	attended in person
2	Lamessa Fekede	Asst. Prof.	Vice Chairperson	attended in person
3	Bulcha Bekele	Asst. Prof.	Secretary	attended in person
4	Arega Wakjira	MSc	Cashier	attended in person
5	Anatol Degefa	Asst. Prof	Auditor	attended in person
6	Emiru Diriba	BSc	Astronomical Software and Innovation -Coordinator	attended in person
7	Dechasa Tolera	PHD Cand.	Wallaga Space Science Triangle Research Team - Co-founder	attended in person through OC invitation
8	Dr. Gemechu Birhanu	DVM	Cultural Astronomy and Diplomacy Research Division -	ESSSDBA's Chairperson also acted on his behalf.

			Coordinator	He raised his hands representing both himself and Dr. Gemechu Birhanu in every election held at the assembly
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The following pictures displays the ESSGA20's participation of ESSS Dambi Dollo, Biftu Begi and Wallaga Branch Association leaders and researchers.

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**ETHIOPIAN SPACE SCIENCE SOCIETY
DAMBI DOLLO BRANCH ASSOCIATION
WALDAA XIINHAWAA ITIYOOPHIYAA
DAMEE DAMBI DOOLLOO**

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**ETHIOPIAN SPACE SCIENCE SOCIETY GENERAL ASSEMBLY TWENTY (ESSSGA-20)
KORA W/G WALDAA XIINHAWAA ITIYOOPHIYAA WAGGAA 20^{FFAA}
እ.ኤ.አ. 2017 ዓ.ም ታዲሳ ፳፻፲፯ ከሚያዝያ 24-26/2017**

Poster designer; Abduselam M., Dachasa T., Emiru D. and Lelisa S
SEENAAN HIN BADU SEERAAN QABANNAAN (QIN. WXIDDD)

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